

Knowledge Absorption at a Global Level

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In the Global Innovation Index (GII), "Knowledge Absorption" refers to a country's or organization's ability to acquire, incorporate, and utilize knowledge generated either internally or externally to improve its capacity for innovation. This component is crucial as it determines how an economy can absorb new technologies, ideas, and know-how from external sources and apply them effectively to promote economic and technological development. "Knowledge Absorption" encompasses various aspects, such as the importation of technology through foreign direct investment, technology licensing, and international collaborations. Additionally, knowledge absorption is enhanced by interactions between local and foreign enterprises, which can lead to technology transfers and the adoption of innovative practices. The role of educational and research institutions is also significant, as they help train a skilled workforce and facilitate the transfer of knowledge. In the context of the GII, a country's ability to absorb knowledge is a key indicator of its global competitiveness. Economies with high knowledge absorption capacities tend to benefit more from globalization, leveraging international networks to accelerate their development. Countries that invest in educational and technological infrastructures and create environments conducive to international collaboration are generally those that show the most progress in terms of innovation. In summary, knowledge absorption is an essential pillar for building an innovative and resilient economy. The data refer to the period between 2013 and 2022.

The Global Knowledge Absorption in 2022. Knowledge absorption is a key indicator for assessing a country's ability to acquire and integrate knowledge from external sources in order to enhance its competitiveness and innovation. By examining the data related to the knowledge absorption of countries in 2022, we can draw several interesting observations. At the top of the ranking, we find Singapore, with a score of 73.3, followed by Luxembourg (66) and Sweden (64). Singapore is notably one of the most advanced technological hubs in the world, with a strong ability to attract foreign investment, technology, and talent from around the globe. Singapore's innovation ecosystem is well-developed, and its commitment to training a highly skilled workforce has allowed the country to excel in knowledge absorption. Luxembourg's position in the ranking is significant, as it represents a small country that has established itself as a financial and technological hub, demonstrating how even small nations can excel in knowledge absorption if they have appropriate policies and advanced technological infrastructures. The presence of Nordic countries such as Sweden (64) and Finland (52.7) in the top ten confirms the importance of a strong educational system and public policies that incentivize research and technological development. These countries are often cited as examples of innovation-driven economies, with strong ties between the public and private sectors and a focus on

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international collaboration, crucial elements for a high capacity for knowledge absorption. Malta (61.2) and Cyprus (56.9) are interesting examples of small island states that have developed strategies to attract investment and expertise from abroad. Their positions in the ranking reflect their ability to use favorable fiscal policies and create attractive environments for technology and research companies. Japan (60.7) stands out as one of the major Asian economies with a high capacity for knowledge absorption, thanks to its industrial and technological strength, which has allowed it to remain competitive on a global scale. Although the country faces demographic challenges and increasing competition from other Asian economies like China and South Korea, Japan continues to demonstrate a high capacity for adaptation and innovation. China (53) and the United States (52.5) are two of the world's largest economies, both with relatively high scores. China, in particular, has made significant progress in recent decades, investing massively in research and development and promoting technology transfer through international collaborations. The enormous domestic market and the Chinese government's commitment to promoting technology and innovation have enabled China to rapidly improve its capacity for knowledge absorption. The United States, despite its tradition of leadership in technological innovation, shows a slightly lower score compared to some European and Asian countries, which could reflect a greater reliance on domestically developed innovations and less need to absorb knowledge from external sources. An interesting aspect is the position of countries like Hungary (55.3) and the Philippines (51.9), which surpass more developed economies such as Germany (45.4) or the United Kingdom (40.6). Hungary has attracted significant foreign investment in the automotive and manufacturing sectors, which has fostered technological transfer and the absorption of advanced skills. The Philippines, on the other hand, has a highly developed outsourcing services sector, relying on technological and linguistic skills to interact with global markets, thus promoting knowledge absorption. Countries traditionally associated with strong innovation, such as Switzerland (49.7), France (49.3), and Germany (45.4), have lower scores compared to other nations. This could reflect the fact that many innovations in these countries are developed internally, reducing the need to absorb external knowledge. However, they remain economies with strong research and development infrastructures, and their capacity for innovation is not in question. A surprising case is the United Kingdom, which, with a score of 40.6, ranks relatively low compared to other advanced economies. This could be attributed to Brexit and the resulting difficulties in maintaining strong ties with European research and innovation, as well as the reduction in international collaboration, which may have reduced its ability to absorb external knowledge. At the bottom of the ranking, we find several countries with very low scores, such as Iraq (14.3), Tajikistan (17), and Bahrain (16.9). These countries, which face significant political, economic, and infrastructural issues, have limited capacity to attract foreign investments and actively participate in global knowledge and innovation networks. The lack of investments in education, technology, and infrastructure drastically reduces their ability to absorb new knowledge and apply it to their economic contexts. In Africa, countries like Nigeria (23.6), Ghana (20.9), and Kenya (26.3) are at the lower end of the ranking. These scores reflect the structural challenges many African economies face, including the lack of technological infrastructure, low levels of investment in research and development, and brain drain. However, some of these countries are making progress in attracting foreign investment and developing tech hubs, such as Kenya, often referred to as the "Silicon Savannah," suggesting that they may improve their knowledge absorption capacity in the future. Latin American countries like Brazil (43.3), Argentina (40.3), and Mexico (34.3) are in the middle or bottom of the ranking, indicating a moderate capacity to absorb knowledge. Latin American economies face similar challenges to those of African countries, such as economic inequality, weak technological infrastructures, and low spending on research and development. However, there are signs of improvement, especially in Brazil, which has seen growth in the technology and agricultural sectors. In conclusion, the 2022 knowledge absorption data highlights strong disparities between countries

with high technological and innovative capacity and those that, for economic, political, or structural reasons, struggle to absorb and integrate new knowledge. Countries like Singapore, Luxembourg, and Sweden are at the forefront of this process, while other nations, especially in Africa and Latin America, face considerable challenges in improving their capacity to integrate global knowledge and foster internal development.

The absorption of knowledge at a global level between 2013 and 2022. Knowledge absorption is a key indicator for assessing a country's ability to acquire, integrate, and exploit external knowledge to stimulate innovation and economic growth. The data we examine, relating to knowledge absorption between 2013 and 2022, show significant variations both in terms of growth and decline in different countries around the world. This analysis allows us to better understand how policies, infrastructures, and socio-economic dynamics can influence a country's ability to absorb new knowledge and adapt it to its context. Among the countries that recorded the most marked growth in knowledge absorption is Yemen, which saw an impressive increase of 679.31%, rising from a score of 2.9 in 2013 to 22.6 in 2022. This increase is particularly significant considering the country's difficult political and economic conditions, suggesting that despite the challenges, Yemen has begun to develop policies and infrastructures that facilitate the acquisition of external knowledge. Angola also shows substantial improvement with a 260% increase, likely due to investments in infrastructure and education, as well as greater integration into global networks. Gulf countries such as Qatar (229%) and Kuwait (135.35%) have also seen significant increases in knowledge absorption, reflecting their ongoing economic diversification. These countries have heavily invested in education, technology, and infrastructure, aiming to reduce their dependence on oil and promote sectors such as scientific research and technological innovation. The United Arab Emirates, with a growth of 125.12%, follows a similar trajectory, seeking to establish itself as a global hub for technology and finance. Another notable case is the Philippines, which saw a 162.12% increase. The Philippines has developed a global outsourcing services sector that requires technological skills and close collaboration with international companies, thus fostering the absorption of external knowledge. This sector has been one of the main contributors to the country's growth in the knowledge absorption index. Similarly, countries like India (137.58%) and Bangladesh (156.16%) have benefited from growing integration into global value chains, with greater exchange of technologies and expertise thanks to globalization. Turkey (111.73%) has also seen considerable growth due to government efforts to modernize the economy, invest in research and development, and attract foreign investment. Its strategic geographical location between Europe and Asia has favored Turkey as a connection point for knowledge exchange between different regions. In East Asia, Japan and South Korea, with increases of 92.09% and 80.50%, respectively, continue to be global leaders in technological innovation and knowledge absorption. Both countries have a long tradition of investment in scientific research and education, factors that make them key players in the global knowledge landscape. However, not all countries have seen positive improvements. Some have shown significant declines in their knowledge absorption between 2013 and 2022. The most dramatic case is Panama, which experienced a 54.27% reduction in its knowledge absorption score, dropping from 46.8 in 2013 to 21.4 in 2022. This decline may reflect economic or political difficulties that have hindered the country's ability to invest in technological infrastructure and innovation projects. Similarly, countries like Guinea (-54.17%) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (-48.94%) have recorded substantial declines, indicating a reduced ability to attract and utilize external knowledge for development. Even countries considered regional hubs for innovation and technology, such as Hong Kong (-26.55%), have shown a decline in knowledge

absorption. This drop could be linked to political tensions and recent changes to Hong Kong's governance, which may have reduced its attractiveness as an international center for finance and innovation. Other countries that have seen significant decreases include Malaysia (-15.82%) and Kenya (-19.57%), both known for their attempts to develop emerging technology sectors but which have evidently encountered structural or political obstacles. Some developed countries have shown only modest improvements or even declines. Singapore, a global leader in innovation, saw a slight decrease of 3.68%. Although Singapore remains one of the most advanced countries in terms of technology and innovation, its slight decline could be due to the fact that, having already reached a very high level of knowledge absorption, the margin for further improvements is limited. Similarly, European countries like Slovenia (-3.55%) and Belgium (-24.24%) have recorded decreases, suggesting they may have faced difficulties in maintaining their pace of innovation and attraction of external knowledge. On the other hand, countries like the United States (+26.81%) and Germany (+28.25%) continue to improve, although at slower rates compared to other emerging nations. This is likely due to the fact that these mature economies have already heavily invested in research and development and, while maintaining a high capacity for innovation, the absorption of external knowledge plays a less critical role compared to developing economies seeking to close the technological gap. It is interesting to note how some sub-Saharan African countries have recorded improvements, such as Ivory Coast (+66.05%) and Ethiopia (+89.51%), highlighting the progress made by some emerging economies in improving their ability to absorb global knowledge. However, these improvements have not been uniform across the region, with countries like Ghana (-45.85%) and Mozambique (-47.84%) seeing significant declines, suggesting that there are persistent structural challenges hindering these countries' growth. In summary, the data on knowledge absorption between 2013 and 2022 show a heterogeneous landscape, where some emerging and developing countries have made significant progress, while others have faced economic, political, or structural challenges that have limited their ability to absorb new knowledge. A country's ability to improve its knowledge absorption is strongly influenced by factors such as investments in technological infrastructure, political stability, and integration into global networks. Countries that manage to balance these elements are able to take full advantage of the opportunities offered by globalization and innovation, while those that fail to do so risk being left behind.

Economic Policies for Knowledge Absorption. Economic policies aimed at increasing knowledge absorption are essential to stimulate innovation and improve a country's competitiveness in the global context. Knowledge absorption refers to an economy's ability to acquire, adapt, and leverage external information and technologies, integrating them into its own production and innovation processes. To achieve this, governments need to adopt a holistic approach that integrates interventions in education, infrastructure, technology, and policy, creating ideal conditions for businesses and institutions to acquire and integrate knowledge. One of the first measures to enhance knowledge absorption is strengthening the educational system, as high-quality education is the foundation for a workforce's ability to assimilate and apply complex knowledge. Policies should focus on increasing investments in schools, universities, and research institutes, with particular attention to STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) disciplines. It is also crucial to promote collaboration between educational institutions and private companies by creating internships, apprenticeships, and continuous training programs, so that students and workers can develop practical and up-to-date skills, facilitating their integration into the workforce. Additionally, encouraging international student and academic mobility can help import knowledge from abroad, fostering cultural and technological exchanges between countries. The creation of a conducive environment for research and development

(R&D) is another key pillar for knowledge absorption. Government policies must encourage innovation through direct financial support, such as grants and tax credits for companies investing in R&D, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises that often struggle to access funding for research projects. At the same time, public-private collaborations should be strengthened, creating technology parks and business incubators where new technologies can be developed and made available to the entrepreneurial sector. Economic policies must incentivize the creation of networks between universities, research centers, and businesses, promoting the sharing of scientific results and the practical application of discoveries. Another intervention area is represented by technological infrastructure. Access to advanced technologies, such as high-quality broadband networks, is essential for knowledge absorption, as it enables rapid and efficient communication between institutions, companies, and individuals. Therefore, governments should invest in modern digital infrastructure, ensuring that the entire population has access to high-speed internet and the necessary technological tools to participate in the knowledge economy. Physical infrastructure, such as transportation and energy systems, are also important for attracting investment and facilitating knowledge exchange by reducing transaction costs and improving the country's internal and external connectivity. Economic policies should also promote a favorable environment for foreign direct investments (FDI), as FDIs represent one of the main sources of technological and knowledge transfer. When a foreign company invests in a country, it often introduces new technologies, management skills, and production methods that local companies can adopt, thus enhancing knowledge absorption at the national level. To attract high-quality investments, governments must create a stable regulatory environment, offer competitive tax incentives, and promote intellectual property protection. Ensuring a transparent and predictable legal framework is essential to attracting innovative companies willing to transfer advanced technologies and establish research centers in the host country. Another crucial aspect for improving knowledge absorption is promoting a culture of innovation and collaboration. Governments can facilitate this process through awareness campaigns and support programs for startups, encouraging entrepreneurship and experimentation. Moreover, the creation of collaborative platforms where companies from different sectors can exchange information and innovative solutions can accelerate knowledge transfer. An open collaborative environment, where data and know-how sharing is encouraged, allows companies to improve their production and innovation processes more quickly. Intellectual property (IP) plays a fundamental role in knowledge absorption. Economic policies must balance the protection of IP rights with the need to promote access to knowledge and technology. While IP rights must be strictly protected to incentivize innovation, policies should also promote licenses and technology transfer agreements that allow local companies to access technologies and ideas developed abroad. Governments can facilitate this process by creating incentives for multinational companies to share their technologies with local partners and supporting the formation of joint ventures between national and foreign companies. Internationally, governments can adopt trade policies that favor the free exchange of technology and knowledge-related goods and services. Participation in multilateral agreements and the reduction of trade barriers can facilitate the import of advanced technologies and promote the exchange of innovative ideas between countries. At the same time, it is important for governments to protect emerging local sectors, allowing them to develop and become competitive internationally before being fully exposed to global competition. A concrete example of successful policies can be found in countries like Singapore, which has built a successful innovation ecosystem through strategic investments in R&D, advanced technological infrastructure, an excellent educational system, and attractive fiscal policies for foreign investors. Singapore's policies focus on creating synergies between the government, businesses, and research institutes, promoting the rapid transfer of knowledge and technologies. Countries such as South Korea and Israel have adopted similar strategies, becoming world leaders in technological innovation through a combination of public

investment in R&D, educational policies, and the attraction of foreign investments. In summary, economic policies to increase knowledge absorption must be integrated and multi-level, covering various areas ranging from education to research, infrastructure to intellectual property. The goal is to create an environment conducive to innovation, where businesses and institutions have the tools and skills to fully exploit the opportunities offered by globalization and technological progress. Promoting knowledge absorption not only strengthens economic competitiveness but also helps create more resilient societies, capable of adapting to global changes and addressing future challenges with greater agility and preparedness.

Conclusions. The data shows an average growth in the knowledge absorption value of 17.58% between 2013 and 2022 for the countries considered. However, some countries performed above the average, namely: Yemen with 679.31%, Angola with 260.00%, Qatar with 229.00%, the Philippines with 162.12%, and Bangladesh with +156.16%. On the other hand, there are countries that saw a significant reduction in the knowledge absorption value, specifically Ghana with -45.85%, Mozambique with -47.84%, Bosnia and Herzegovina with -48.94%, Guinea with -54.17%, and Panama with -54.27%.

Performers	Countries	2013	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Top Performers</i>	<i>Yemen, Rep.</i>	2,9	22,6	19,7	679,31
	<i>Angola</i>	5	18	13	260,00
	<i>Qatar</i>	10	32,9	22,9	229,00
	<i>Philippines</i>	19,8	51,9	32,1	162,12
	<i>Bangladesh</i>	7,3	18,7	11,4	156,16
<i>Worse Performers</i>	<i>Ghana</i>	38,6	20,9	-17,7	-45,85
	<i>Mozambique</i>	46,2	24,1	-22,1	-47,84
	<i>Bosnia and Herzegovina</i>	37,6	19,2	-18,4	-48,94
	<i>Guinea</i>	40,8	18,7	-22,1	-54,17
	<i>Panama</i>	46,8	21,4	-25,4	-54,27

Fonte: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://www.wipo.int/web/global-innovation-index>

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